

Exploring the Custom Design of Women's Dress Based on Digital Application

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ABSTRACT: This paper explores the application of Digital Technology in the custom design of women's dress. By looking into the background of the industrial development, it clarifies the concept and characteristics of Digital Technology and puts forward the basic customization path for custom-made women's dress. The advantages of Digital Technology use are then analyzed from the aspects of design measurement, production and marketing, so as to build a whole picture for the process application of digital customization supported by four technologies: anthropometry, virtual display, intelligent design and artificial intelligence. Finally, the paper provides targeted recommendation for optimization from the three levels of technology, process and user, aiming to resolve the contradiction between traditional hand-made customization and industrial mass production, realizing the balance between individualization and scale, and providing theoretical and practical reference for digital customization of women's dress.

KEYWORDS: Digital Technology; Women's Dress; Custom design; Digital customization

1. BACKGROUND

1.1. Digital Technology drives development of industry

In recent years, China has elevated her digital development to a national strategic level and built a systematic policy support system and strategic layout. In May 2025, the State Council issued the 2025 Action Plan to Build Digital China, proposing that by the end of 2025, the added value of the core industries from the digital economy will account for more than 10% of GDP, and deploying special actions encompassing eight key areas including artificial intelligence, infrastructure and digital talents, etc., providing a clear top-level guidance for industrial digital transformation. In the cultural field, the revenue of core national cultural sectors exceeded RMB 10.3 trillion in 2025, indicating that the cultural assets were accelerating their conversion into commercial value. The 2024 Blue Book on the Innovative Development of China's Digital Art evaluates the multi-dimensional performance of digital art innovation, giving an in-depth analysis for the status quo and challenges of China's digital art development, and provides theoretical support and practical references for the future development of digital art.

Scholars at home and abroad have achieved relatively systematic research results on the integration of Digital Technology and custom design. Multi-dimensional explorations have been conducted in aspects such as anthropometric technology, 3D modeling, personalized pattern making, virtual display, as well as innovation in customization systems and digital design models. Digital Technology is gradually connecting the entire process chain of the fashion industry from front-end experience, mid-end design to back-end manufacturing, laying foundation for improving garment custom design.

1.2. Development Context of Chinese Contemporary Women's Dress

The origin of modern women's dress may be traced back to the European court costume system of the 17th-18th centuries. In China, a country of clothes, the ceremonial dress has always been an important carrier of Chinese etiquette civilization. From the foundation of the pre-Qin coronary dress system, to the folklorization of phoenix coronet and robes of rank in Ming and Qing Dynasties, and then to the fusion of the West to the East in modern times, a Dress Code system with ceremonial system as the core has been built. Its fabrics, colors, patterns and shapes follows social hierarchy and ceremonial context strictly^[1]. The "Dress Code" promulgated by the Beiyang government in 1912 directed that women's dress should be in the style of a jacket with a skirt. The fashion culture in Shanghai modern history, as represented by Shanghai-style suits and Shanghai-style cheongsams, pushed the development of the custom-made industry, giving birth to two major tailor faction: the "Shanghai Local" and "Ningbo Local", which combined Chinese and Western styles^[2]. The leap in consumption capacity triggered by nearly half a century of China's Reform and Opening up has accelerated the Westernization wave in the field of formal dresses. Women have been liberated further in their clothing choices, forming a diversified pattern of integration between Chinese and Western styles.

2. OVERVIEW OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY AND BASIC CUSTOMIZATION PATH FOR CUSTOM-MADE OF WOMEN'S DRESS

2.1. The Concept of Digital Technology

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Digitalization refers to the process of converting complex and variable information, such as signals and data from images, videos, texts, sounds, etc., into measurable computer binary codes, i.e., combinations and changes of 0s and 1s, which are then transmitted to the computer to build a digital model for unified processing. This is the digitalization process^[3]. Digital technology is not an individual technology but a cluster of technologies, including but not limited to data acquisition technology, digital signal processing technology, data storage and compression technology, computer graphics, database management systems, and various software and hardware collaboration platforms. Collectively, these technologies realize the mapping, modeling, and manipulation from the physical world to the digital world, providing a universal foundation for the development of various industries. Digital transformation has risen from a mere technological option to a strategic necessity for enterprise survival and development, becoming a key path to reshape industrial resilience and competitive positioning.

2.2. Characteristics of the Application of Digital Technology in the Design Field

To explain how digital technology drives design innovation, we need to start from its inherent characteristics. The application of digital technology in the design field is essentially a systematic summary of existing design experience and long-term practice, which is transformed into computable, modifiable, and storable design rules and operation methods by means of digitalization. Combining the dual attributes of digital technology and design activities, the following three basic characteristics are summarized:

(1) Data-Driven

Digital technology takes data as the core element for production, while processes and systems serve data collection and analysis rather than being reversely dependent. Relying on a unified data platform, real-time integration of multi-source heterogeneous information, it drives decision-making and innovation through mining and modeling, realizing a fundamental transformation from experience-driven to data intelligence, and improving response speed and accuracy.

(2) Interconnectivity Collaboration

Digitalization is not a partial improvement but a systematic transformation that runs through all business processes of an enterprise and breaks down departmental barriers. By using technologies such as the Internet of Things and cloud computing, what it achieves are the comprehensive connection of people, machines, and things, establishing an ecological network of data intercommunication, business collaboration, and resource sharing. Information flows freely in design, production, service and other links, realizing open sharing and efficient allocation of resources. Upstream and downstream of the supply chain may synchronize demand and capacity in real time, greatly reducing information asymmetry, and improving operational flexibility and overall efficiency.

(3) Intelligent Efficiency

Digital technologies have greatly improved the efficiency and accuracy of information processing. By leveraging advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence, machine learning, and big data analysis, enterprises can achieve automated and intelligent decision-making and services. Digitalization also enables repetitive work to be completed quickly and in batches. From production scheduling to inventory management, from quality inspection to personalized recommendations, intelligent efficiency is reflected in every aspect of enterprise operations and has become a core driving force for enhancing competitiveness.

2.3 Basic Customization Path of Digital Technology in Women's Dress

In view of the data-driven, collaborative interconnectivity, and intelligent efficiency as reflected in digital technologies, a new ecological system that is open and inclusive, cross-subject collaborative, and operates intelligently and efficiently, has been established for product design and development activities. Considering the entire process of clothing product development, this study proposes an implementation path for integrating Digital Technology with custom-made of Women's dress (see Figure 1). This path could be sub-divided into five key stages: Demand insight and analysis stage, creative design conceptualization stage, intelligent manufacturing execution stage, marketing strategy stage, and user data feedback stage. This path helps systematically clarify how Digital Technology could achieve innovative breakthroughs at each key node, thus driving the continuous optimization of custom-made process for Women's dress.

Figure 1: Basic Customization Path of Digital Technology in Women's Dress

Image Source: Drawn by the Author

3. APPLICATION AND ANALYSIS OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY IN CUSTOM-MADE OF WOMEN'S DRESS

3.1. Advantages of Combining Digital Technology with Dress Custom Design

Traditional customization takes the handmade craftsmanship as the core and relies heavily on the practical experience of the craftsmen. Although it boasts high cultural added value and social emotional value, its labor-intensive nature results in long production cycles and limited economies of scale. With the continuous improvement of industrialization and informatization, garment production has gradually shifted to assembly line-based large-scale manufacturing, leading to a significant increase in production efficiency. However, the path of standardized production has also triggered issues such as product homogenization, increased inventory backlog risks, and quality fluctuations, making it an inevitable bottleneck restricting the sustainable development of the industry. Both models of traditional handmade custom design and industrial mass production have their limitations and have always struggled to balance personalized expression, production efficiency, and market adaptability. The rise of digital technology has provided a new approach to resolving this industry contradiction. Therefore, this study defines the core concept in the intersection area of three dimensions: personalized customization, digital technology, and fashion design (see Figure 2). Below, the author will explain the advantages brought by the integration of digital technology and women's dress custom design from the aspects of design, measurement, production, and marketing.

Figure 2: Schematic Diagram of Core Concept Definition for Digital Application in Custom-made of Women's Dress

Image Source: Drawn by the Author

(1) Design and Measurement

In view of the industrial pain points, traditional custom design in women's dress has long faced the core contradiction of unbalance in between formfitting and efficiency. On one hand, due to the complex styles of dresses, such as corsets and mermaid skirts, which propose extremely high requirements for clothing fit, traditional measurement relies on personal experience, which may lead to poor fit easily even after repeated fittings due to errors in body shape data. On the other hand, the production cost of physical samples is high with long cycle, making it difficult for customers to intuitively predict the final effect, which often leads to disputes due to the large gap between expectations and the finished product. With the increasing maturity of science and technology, the application of anthropometric technology and virtual fitting technology provides a new path to solve this contradiction.

Three-dimensional non-contact anthropometric measurement methods include laser measurement, Moiré fringe scanning, 3D scanning, white light phase method, etc^[4]. Mainstream laser 3D human body scanning equipment in the international market includes Cyberware WB4 multimodal scanner, 3DLS dynamic capture system, Hamamatsu non-contact scanner, etc^[5]. Cyberware WB4, the world's first commercial laser 3D human body scanner in the clothing field, adopts multi-CCD laser array detection technology. It synchronously collects human body surface deformation data through four sets of line structured light sensors and generates high-precision 3D models through multi-view point cloud registration algorithms. The system can output RGB color human body meshes with a resolution of 0.5mm, shorten the single full-body scanning cycle to 12 seconds, and control the measurement repeatability error within $\pm 5\text{mm}$ ^[6].

(2) Production and Marketing

Intelligent CAD systems can automatically generate and optimize dress patterns based on customers' detailed anthropometric measurements and unique body shape characteristics, enabling real-time adjustment of personalized tailoring solutions to ensure that each dress perfectly fits the wearer's figure. The integrated application of digital manufacturing technologies such as Computer-Aided Manufacturing (CAM), Computer-Aided Process Planning (CAPP), and Flexible Manufacturing Systems (FMS) can support the construction of large-scale flexible production models. Relying on flexible strategies such as multi-variety mixed-line production, intelligent scheduling, and robot collaboration, it realizes multi-category, differentiated, and short-cycle product delivery, effectively reducing the production cost per unit.

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Digital marketing has become a core driver for the transformation and upgrading of various industries. The clothing customization field has also reconstructed marketing logic and user interaction models through the integration and innovation of digital technologies and new media. Traditional clothing marketing is mostly dominated by one-way brand output, where users passively receive product information, resulting in a lack of participation and personalization in the purchasing experience. Digital marketing, relying on technologies such as the Internet, computer communications, and digital interactions, is transiting users from passive audiences into active participants by breaking down online and offline experience barriers and building immersive interactive scenarios, achieving dual improvements in marketing value and user experience. Intelligent big data analysis technology may provide in-depth analysis and extract key information such as fashion preferences, price tolerance, and lifestyle patterns displayed by consumers in their daily clothing choices and then leverage this information to create detailed and accurate user behavior portraits. Based on this, clothing recommendation systems using big data and AI technologies have emerged, which can provide customers with comprehensive personalized suggestions from fabric selection to style design. The integrated application of digital marketing technologies, such as 3D virtual fitting rooms, VR virtual exhibition halls, and AR augmented reality, is transforming traditional flat product browsing into a three-dimensional and in-depth interactive participation process. Users will increase their favorability towards the brand due to personalized immersive experiences, and then spontaneously share the customization process and results through social platforms, forming fission-style communication and helping to accurately convey the brand spirit and product value.

3.2. The Application of Digital Technology in Custom Design of Women's Dresses

From the analysis of the above aspects, it can be seen that the combination of digital technology and dress customization design can effectively solve the industry pain points of insufficient scale in traditional manual customization and serious homogenization in industrial mass production, empowering industrial upgrading in an all-round way. At the design level, relying on technologies such as intelligent anthropometric measurement and virtual fitting, it accurately satisfies those personalized customization needs and improves the efficiency of design implementation; At the production level, with the help of various digital intelligent manufacturing systems, it realizes flexible and precise production, taking into account both customization quality and production control; At the marketing level, through big data analysis and virtual interaction technologies, it optimizes the experience and accurately connects with market demand. The three major links work together to effectively balance the personalized expression, production efficiency and market adaptability of dress customization, providing solid technical support and innovative directions for the long-term development of the industry.

Figure 3: Flowchart of Using Digital Technology in Custom Design of Women's Dress

Image Source: Drawn by the Author

Figure 3 presents the complete process of digital technology empowering women's formal wear customization, with digital technology as the core. It relies on anthropometric measurement technology to accurately collect body shape data, uses virtual display technology to complete the digital presentation of clothing, leverages intelligent design technology to match personalized customization needs, and finally optimizes production and data analysis through artificial intelligence technology to achieve precise and intelligent upgrading of the entire formal wear customization process.

Although digital technology has brought efficiency improvements and experience optimization to the custom-made of women's dress, in the real-world application process, challenges exist for the in-depth adaptation between technical tools and customization demands. The current digital customization model still has structural shortcomings in technical aspects, process design, and user services, restricting its leap from usable to user-friendly.

4. CONCLUSION: OPTIMIZATION SUGGESTIONS FOR DIGITAL CUSTOMIZATION OF WOMEN'S DRESS

Finally, this paper puts forward optimization suggestions for digital customization of women's dress from three aspects: technology, process, and users, to achieve a closed loop from theory to practical implementation.

4.1. Technical Level: Building an Exclusive Digital Asset Library and Craft Knowledge Graph for Formal Wear

Enterprises related to women's dress should systematically build an exclusive digital asset library for the women's dress category, covering a high-fidelity digital fabric library and a 3D pattern library of typical styles, to provide reusable and expandable basic resources for digital customization. Simplify complex formal dress craftsmanship into standardized parameter modules and construct a craftsmanship knowledge spectrum for AI-powered design systems to calling and combine. While reducing reliance on the experience of senior designers, it improves the standardization level and replicability of customized solutions, providing technical support for balancing personalization and scale.

4.2. Process Level: Adopt a customized process that coordinates online visualization with offline touchpoints

Enterprises should adjust and optimize traditional linear customization processes, integrate pre-customization and mid-customization processes, move standardized links such as demand communication and scheme visualization to online platforms in advance, and realize remote collaboration and real-time feedback with the help of 3D digital samples and real-time rendering technology to improve the efficiency of early decision-making. Keep core links related to fit and trust building, such as 3D anthropometric measurement and final garment inspection, as key offline service touchpoints to ensure customization accuracy and brand professional value, creating a high-quality and customized service experience.

4.3. User Level: Deepen virtual fitting experience and data privacy protection

Based on the digital 3D model, enterprises can develop lightweight AR fitting applications adapted to mobile terminals, so that users can initially perceive the upper body effect and style fitting of dresses online, and reduce the psychological threshold and time cost of customized decision-making. In the process of collecting and using user body shape data, a transparent and contractual data governance mechanism should be established to clearly inform the scope of data collection, storage period, encryption protection standards and third-party sharing restrictions, and ensure that users have the right to access, correct and delete their personal data. By building a trusted data privacy protection system, resolve consumers' potential concerns about the promotion of digital customization services, and lay a user trust foundation for the large-scale application of customization models.

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